

Knowledge-Guided Optimization for Complex Vehicle Routing with 3D Loading Constraints: Supplementary Material

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1 Problem formulation

This section presents the mathematical formulation of 3L-SDVRP, supporting Section 2.1 of the main text.

1.1 Notations

Consider a network that includes N customer nodes and a depot, designated as both the starting and ending points with indices 0 and $N + 1$, respectively. The pairwise distances among all nodes are known in advance. At each node, a unique set of boxes is available, with each box characterized by its weight and three-dimensional size—specifically, its length, width, and height. The objective is to optimally assign vehicles for the transportation of all boxes, originating from their respective nodes to the terminal depot, with all vehicles commencing their journeys from this starting point. The notations used in the mathematical formulation are shown in Table 1.

1.2 A mathematical model

The following mathematical model is constructed based on [8]. There are two objectives relevant to both routing and packing aspects of the problem. The first one:

$$\min f_1 = n \quad (1)$$

In Eq. (1), n is the number of vehicles used.

The second one:

$$\min f_2 = \sum_{t=1}^n \sum_{i=0}^{N+1} \sum_{j=0}^{N+1} d_{ij} X_{ij}^t \quad (2)$$

The optimization process is guided by two conflicting objective functions: f_1 and f_2 . Objective f_1 focuses on minimizing the total number of vehicles utilized, while objective f_2 aims to reduce the total travel distance (ttd) across all vehicles.

Table 1. Notations used in the mathematical formulation

Notations	Description
$G = (V, E)$	road network, a complete directed graph
$V = \{0, 1, \dots, N, N + 1\}$	the set of vertices; 0 is the starting point; $N + 1$ is the ending point; $1 \sim N$ are nodes/customers
$E = \{(i, j) \mid i, j \in V, i \neq j\}$	the set of edges
d_{ij}	non-negative travel distance, $d_{ij} \neq d_{ji}$
$O = \{K_i \mid i = 1, \dots, M\}$	one delivery order/dataset; $1 \leq M \leq N$
$K_i = \{1, \dots, m_i\}$	the set of boxes that need to be transported in the node i ; m_i : # boxes in the node i
$A_i^t \subset K_i$	the set of boxes that are loaded in vehicle t in the node i
l_k, w_k, h_k	the length, width, and height of the box k
q_k, v_k	the weight and volume of the box k
x_k, y_k, z_k	the coordinate of the center of the box k
$L_t, W_t, H_t, t = 1, \dots, n$	the length, width, height of container vehicle t ; n : total # vehicles used to transport boxes
$Q_t, t = 1, \dots, n$	the weight capacity of container vehicle t
X_{ij}^t	= 1 if vehicle t travels from node i to j ; = 0 otherwise; $(i, j = 0, 1, \dots, N + 1; t = 1, \dots, n)$
x_{k1}, y_{k1}, z_{k1}	the smallest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the box k in the vehicle.
x_{k2}, y_{k2}, z_{k2}	the largest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the box k in the vehicle
x_{t1}, y_{t1}, z_{t1}	the smallest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the container of the vehicle t (the origin of the coordinate system)
x_{t2}, y_{t2}, z_{t2}	the largest $x, y,$ and z coordinates of the container of the vehicle t

Consistent with current research [3–5, 8, 9, 12], we treat the inherently bi-objective 3L-SDVRP as a single-objective optimization problem. In this framework, our primary focus is on minimizing the number of vehicles used, while the secondary objective is to reduce the total travel distance (with lower priority) [3].

The constraints are as follows.

$$\sum_{j=1}^N X_{0j}^t = 1, t = 1, \dots, n \quad (3)$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^N X_{i(N+1)}^t = 1, t = 1, \dots, n \quad (4)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^N X_{ik}^t = \sum_{j=1}^{N+1} X_{kj}^t, k = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (5)$$

$$\sum_{i=0; i \neq j}^N X_{ij}^t \leq 1, j = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (6)$$

$$\delta_1 (x_{k2} - x_{l1}) (x_{l2} - x_{k1}) \leq 0, k, l \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (7)$$

$$\delta_2 (y_{k2} - y_{l1}) (y_{l2} - y_{k1}) \leq 0, k, l \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (8)$$

$$\delta_3 (z_{k2} - z_{l1}) (z_{l2} - z_{k1}) \leq 0, k, l \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_1, \delta_2, \delta_3 \in \{0, 1\}, \delta_1 + \delta_2 + \delta_3 \geq 1 \quad (10)$$

$$\bigcup_{t=1, \dots, n} A_i^t = K_i, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (11)$$

$$\bigcap_{t=1, \dots, n} A_i^t = \emptyset, i = 1, \dots, N \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{b \in B_k} [\min \{x_{b2} - x_{k1}, x_{k2} - x_{b1}\} \cdot \min \{y_{b2} - y_{k1}, y_{k2} - y_{b1}\}] \geq p \cdot w_k l_k \quad (13)$$

$$k \in A_i^t, t = 1, \dots, n; i = 1, \dots, N;$$

B_k : the set of boxes under and touching the box k in vehicle t

$$\sum_{k \in A_i^t} q_k \leq Q_t, i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (14)$$

$$x_{k1} \geq x_{t1}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (15)$$

$$y_{k1} \geq y_{t1}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (16)$$

$$z_{k1} \geq z_{t1}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (17)$$

$$x_{k2} \leq x_{t2}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (18)$$

$$y_{k2} \leq y_{t2}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (19)$$

$$z_{k2} \leq z_{l2}, k \in A_i^t; i = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (20)$$

$$I_k > I_l, \text{ if Eq. (22, 23, 25) or Eq. (23, 24, 26) hold simultaneously.} \quad (21)$$

In Eq. (21):

$$k \in A_i^t; l \in A_j^t; i, j = 1, \dots, N; t = 1, \dots, n \quad (21a)$$

$$I_k, I_l : \text{loading order of box } k \text{ and } l \text{ in vehicle } R_t \quad (21b)$$

$$(x_{k2} - x_{l1})(x_{l2} - x_{k1}) > 0 \quad (22)$$

$$(y_{k2} - y_{l1})(y_{l2} - y_{k1}) > 0 \quad (23)$$

$$(z_{k2} - z_{l1})(z_{l2} - z_{k1}) > 0 \quad (24)$$

$$z_{k1} \geq z_{l2} \quad (25)$$

$$x_{k1} \geq x_{l2} \quad (26)$$

In this study, constraints are categorized into two main aspects: vehicle routing and 3D loading.

1. **Vehicle Routing Constraints:** Equations (3)–(5) define valid route formation. Each route initiates at a starting node and terminates at an ending node. The depot often serves as both the starting and ending nodes. Additionally, flow conservation must be maintained, meaning that the number of vehicles entering and exiting a node must be equal. Equation (6) enforces a single-visit requirement, ensuring that each customer is visited by the same vehicle only once.
2. **3D Loading Constraints:** *Non-overlapping:* Equations (7)–(10) specify that boxes within the same vehicle must not overlap in any dimension. *Non-splitting:* Equations (11)–(12) dictate that each box can be loaded into only one vehicle. *Supporting Stability:* Equation (13) requires that the supporting area of each box must be at least a percentage p of its bottom area (with $p = 1.0$ in this study). *Weight Capacity:* Equation (14) restricts the total weight of loaded boxes to the vehicle's weight capacity. *Size:* Equations (15)–(20) ensure that boxes must be contained within the vehicle's container without exceeding the container walls or doors. *Last-In-First-Out (LIFO):* Equations (21)–(26) specify that boxes loaded later must be unloaded first, once a vehicle departs from a node.

2 Large Step Size of AKI Operator

This section introduce the detailed method for calculating the number of swaps and shifts equivalent to one AKI operation, supporting Section 3.2 of the main text.

To demonstrate its larger step size, the AKI operator was empirically tested on 100 random giant tours. We applied AKI once per giant tour and compared its effect to traditional Swap and Shift operators, calculating the average operations needed for similar results. Specifically, given a giant tour denoted as a , the AKI operator produces a new tour b . We then apply Swap and Shift operators multiple times to transform a into b , calculating the minimum number of operations required for both Swap and Shift operators. The calculation methods are detailed in Algorithms 1 and 2.

Algorithm 1 Calculate the Minimum Number of Swaps

Input: a : the original giant tour; b : the giant tour generated from a after applying the AKI operator

Output: $swaps$: the minimum number of swaps to convert a into b

```

1: if len( $a$ ) is not equal to len( $b$ ) or set of  $a$  is not equal to set of  $b$  then
2:   raise ValueError("Giant tours 'a' and 'b' must have the same elements and
   length.")
3: end if
4:  $index\_map \leftarrow \{\text{value: index for index, value in enumerate}(b)\}$ 
5:  $swaps \leftarrow 0$ 
6: for  $i \leftarrow 0$  to length of  $a$  do
7:    $correct\_value \leftarrow b[i]$ 
8:   if  $a[i] \neq correct\_value$  then
9:      $swap\_index \leftarrow index\_map[a[i]]$ 
10:    Swap  $a[i]$  and  $a[swap\_index]$ 
11:    Update  $index\_map$  after the swap
12:     $index\_map[a[swap\_index]] \leftarrow swap\_index$ 
13:     $swaps \leftarrow swaps + 1$ 
14:   end if
15: end for
16: return  $swaps$ 

```

3 Packing Method in the AKS Algorithm

This section introduce the packing method used in the AKS algorithm, supporting Section 3.3 of the main text.

In its packing process, the AKS algorithm employs various heuristics and selects the packing plan that minimizes space occupation. One such heuristic, based on research from [3, 2], involves constructing vertical layers. In this context,

Algorithm 2 Calculate the Minimum Number of Insertions

Input: a : the original giant tour; b : the giant tour generated from a after applying the AKI operator

Output: $inversions$: the minimum number of insertions to convert a into b

```

1: if  $\text{len}(a)$  is not equal to  $\text{len}(b)$  or set of  $a$  is not equal to set of  $b$  then
2:   raise ValueError("Giant tours 'a' and 'b' must have the same elements and
   length.")
3: end if
   // Create a map  $index\_map$  to store the index of each element in list  $b$ 
4: for each  $index, value$  in  $\text{enumerate}(b)$  do
5:    $index\_map[value] \leftarrow index$ 
6: end for
   // Convert  $a$  to a list of indices  $indexed\_a$  according to the order of elements in  $b$ 
7: for each  $value$  in  $a$  do
8:   Append  $index\_map[value]$  to  $indexed\_a$ 
9: end for
10:  $lis\_length \leftarrow$  calculate the length of the longest increasing subsequence in
     $indexed\_a$ 
11:  $inversions \leftarrow \text{len}(a) - lis\_length$ 
12: return  $inversions$ 

```

“space” refers to an available rectangular cuboid area for loading boxes. Placing a box in a space means aligning it with the space’s left-bottom-rear corner. Inserting a box into this space disrupts the original space and creates new smaller spaces (subspaces) for unpacked boxes. If s_{curr} is the current space and S_{avail} the set of all available spaces, this method loads two boxes at a time. First, one box goes into s_{curr} , creating three new subspaces. Then, a second box is placed in one of these subspaces, with the other two subspaces added to S_{avail} . Notably, the second box does not create additional subspaces. If it’s not possible to find two suitable boxes, just one box fitting into s_{curr} is loaded.

Another packing strategy used in the AKS algorithm is based on extreme points (EP), a concept introduced by [6] and further used in various studies [1, 11, 4, 7, 10]. An EP is a point created by projecting along the coordinate axes when a box is loaded into a space, representing a new available space for unpacked boxes. One EP is typically the bottom-left-back vertex of a space. In this EP-based method, loading each box creates new EPs, thus generating new subspaces. These, along with previously existing spaces, are used for loading more boxes. This procedure continues until all boxes are successfully loaded.

Our routing-packing interactive strategy is based on the approach proposed in [13], which enables adaptive packing decision-making during route planning. This strategy decides whether to load boxes at a node individually or together with boxes from the next node. Individual loading adheres to the packing-first-routing-second (P1R2) strategy, while joint loading of two nodes uses the two-customer segment pattern (2C-SP) [3]. This adaptivity allows for adjustments in packing during the routing process, aligning with the routing-first-packing-second (R1P2) strategy.

4 Giant Tour Decoding in the AKS algorithm

This section introduces the giant tour decoding process used in the AKS algorithm, supporting Section 3.3 of the main text.

As mentioned earlier, a giant tour includes all nodes but isn't a feasible solution for the 3L-SDVRP. Developing feasible solutions is complex, involving not just creating routes but also developing detailed loading plans (e.g., the order and spatial coordinate of each box) for multiple vehicles.

Decoding a giant tour is the process of turning it into a feasible solution. Here's how it works: For a given giant tour, vehicles visit nodes in sequence, focusing on those that haven't been loaded yet. At each node, they assess two scenarios: loading boxes from only the current node versus loading boxes from both the current and the next node. This involves comparing the space efficiency of the box loading plans for each scenario. The vehicle then chooses the plan that occupies the least space. This method optimizes the use of vehicle space, potentially reducing the number of vehicles required. For a more detailed explanation of the decoding process, readers are referred to [3].

5 Experimental Data

This section provides the raw data of experiments, supporting Section 4 of the main text. The experiments were conducted on three widely-recognized benchmark datasets in the field of 3L-SDVRP: the B-Y instances [3], Shanghai instances [3], and SD instances [4]. Instances were divided into two categories: those with fewer than 100 nodes were labeled as small-scale, while those containing 100 to 200 nodes were classified as large-scale datasets.

5.1 Features of New Problem Instances

Table 2 shows features of new problem instances created based on existing ones by changing the node distribution.

Table 2. Description of new instances

Entry	# nodes	# box types	# boxes
Min	43	14	284
Max	200	634	8060
Avg	85.3	146.1	4473.8

5.2 Experimental Results of Different Methods

Experimental Results on Dataset from Literature Tables 3 and 4 present the raw experimental results of different algorithms on three widely recognized

datasets: the B-Y instances [3], Shanghai instances [3], and SD instances [4]. Problem instances with fewer than 100 nodes were classified as small-scale, while those with 100 to 200 nodes were considered larger-scale.

SDVRLH2 [3] is the state-of-the-art algorithm for 3L-SPVRP. AKS is our proposed algorithm which uses the AKI operator. LS and AKS differ because LS does not perform node insertion. LSP and LSC utilize Proximity and Connectivity rules, respectively.

Experimental Results on New Problem Instances Tables 5 and 6 present the raw experimental results of different algorithms on new problem instances created by this paper.

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Table 3. Experimental results of SDVRLH2 and AKS algorithms. SDVRLH2 [3] is the state-of-the-art algorithm for 3L-SPVRP. AKS is our proposed algorithm which uses the AKI operator. # v = the number of vehicles used; ttd = total travel distance; # FE = the number of fitness evaluations. LB = lower bound.

Instances (small)	SDVRLH2 (SD)					AKS				
	Avg		Best		# FE	Avg		Best		# FE
	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	LB	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg
B-Y1	37	2081.6	37	2081.6	481696	36	2026.92	36	1988.30	25683.1
B-Y2	15.5	1055.29	15	1044.2	481696	14	1032.07	14	972.60	32091.7
B-Y3	37	2071	37	2071	481696	36	2006.98	36	1963.20	23075.3
B-Y4	18	1184.62	18	1149.6	481696	17.9	1156.99	17	1133.40	27715.8
B-Y5	54	2961.2	54	2961.2	1057296	53	2917.46	53	2857.00	63693.3
B-Y6	25	1570.72	25	1541.4	1057296	23.8	1532.49	23	1511.90	62617.6
B-Y7	57	3215.8	57	3215.8	1057296	55.13	3092.61	55	3033.50	92272.1
B-Y8	26	1645.03	26	1606.8	1057296	25	1587.07	25	1557.70	62910.0
Sha1	3	562.6	3	562.6	1816	3	562.60	3	562.60	207.9
Sha2	9	2786.6	9	2786.6	5900	9	2845.88	9	2824.40	559.3
Sha3	4	396.48	4	393	17936	4	387.65	4	381.10	739.6
Sha4	4	350.33	4	349.7	22500	4	357.01	4	350.10	1000.3
Sha5	6	1451.27	6	1447.6	13140	5	1210.82	5	1200.60	952.7
Sha6	8	482.13	8	479.6	39856	7	453.15	7	432.10	1598.5
Sha7	12	1707.48	12	1694.8	45340	11	1603.84	11	1580.52	2202.8
Sha8	8	357.67	8	352.7	30080	8	344.32	8	337.73	2704.0
Sha9	13	944.28	13	928.7	116240	12.4	912.45	12	896.10	7482.6
Sha10	14	1605.36	14	1590.1	115440	14	1618.69	14	1582.80	8519.0
Sha11	26.2	523.21	26	521.5	575640	26	518.90	26	507.40	26539.3
Sha12	17	2968.08	17	2942.1	250736	15	2724.64	15	2639.00	13959.1
Sha13	27.7	3147.93	27	3097.3	907644	27	3162.17	27	3103.33	55744.2
SD1	5	5238.5	5	4941.8	13680	5	5171.90	5	5062.11	804.9
SD2	14	11929.8	14	11620.2	99096	13	10774.49	13	10668.36	5406.4
SD3	23	16302.1	23	15800.9	154480	23	15881.28	23	15536.47	9518.1
SD4	14	12826.7	14	12655.5	225400	13	12148.36	13	11919.93	11783.5
SD5	17	14513.8	17	14513.8	315040	18	14901.98	18	14769.74	16075.7
SD6	17	15883.7	17	15332.5	272960	14	13858.25	14	13593.26	19506.6
SD7	13	12206.6	13	11804.4	342776	10	10627.42	10	10077.22	24037.2
SD8	23	19709.8	23	19225.8	394140	19	17137.64	19	16487.10	25364.6
SD9	20	16512.9	20	16015	551820	16.03	14687.68	16	13980.75	35486.0
SD10	18	16432.6	18	15874.5	569236	8	10263.84	8	9743.47	39524.3
SD11	21.1	18871.3	21	18593.2	2197140	9	11258.45	9	10913.21	93686.2
Avg	19.0	6046.77	18.9	5912.36	419812.63	17.3	5273.94	17.3	5130.22	24795.68
Total	606.5	193496.48	605	189195.5	13434004	554.3	168765.98	552	164167.00	793461.73

Instances (large)	SDVRLH2 (SD)					AKS				
	Avg		Best		# FE	Avg		Best		#FE
	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	LB	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg
B-Y9	71	4014.9	71	4014.9	2041396	70	3963.71	70	3897.00	152132.3
B-Y10	34.7	2133.53	34	2077.3	2041396	31.9	2050.57	31	2003.60	140108.6
B-Y11	76	4386.7	76	4386.6	2041396	73.7	4143.22	73	4124.40	145778.8
B-Y12	34	2173.56	34	2151.3	2041396	33.5	2165.16	33	2118.80	150926.2
B-Y13	109	6043.42	109	6022.4	5332096	106.6	5730.94	106	5693.00	417734.5
B-Y14	48	2942.14	48	2888.3	5332096	45.73	2833.62	45	2759.20	403574.4
B-Y15	117.6	6477.68	117	6451.1	5332096	110	5947.96	110	5893.40	451011.3
B-Y16	51.9	3089.77	51	3177.8	5332096	50.6	3025.96	50	2976.10	405869.6
B-Y17	148	8462.34	148	8456.4	11464784	141.67	7426.79	140	7374.00	889096.7
B-Y18	65.6	3676.74	65	3647.1	11464784	59.37	3515.71	59	3444.80	911878.6
B-Y19	154	9298.8	154	9296.4	11464784	143.93	7554.89	143	7483.80	811376.2
B-Y20	74.6	4298.52	73	4351.4	11464784	69.97	4066.36	69	3989.70	961463.3
Sha14	44.2	1574.4	44	1522.5	3325320	43	1528.61	43	1440.40	141224.6
Sha15	71.9	4866.99	71	4795.4	17234796	68	4606.08	68	4417.63	855582.7
SD12	44	37261.3	44	36311.5	3713304	43	35403.56	43	34877.74	277875.1
SD13	25	22047.5	25	21694.3	3713304	20	19284.66	20	18965.66	287808.8
Avg	73.1	7671.77	72.8	7577.79	6458739.25	69.4	7077.99	68.9	6966.20	462715.11
Total	1169.5	122748.29	1164	121244.7	103339828	1110.97	113247.80	1103	111459.23	7403441.73

Table 5. Experimental results of different methods. AKS is our proposed algorithm which uses the AKI operator. LSrdm randomly selects between Proximity and Connectivity rules. # v = the number of vehicles used; ttd = total travel distance; # FE = the number of fitness evaluations.

Instances	AKS					LSrdm				
	Avg		Best		#FE	Avg		Best		#FE
	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg
Ins1	14	14299.77	14	13976.17	19011.5	14	14395.12	14	14156.58	17425.2
Ins2	14	14445.55	14	14011.72	19208.3	14	14473.49	14	14173.36	18316.3
Ins3	14	14519.49	14	14150.28	18119.2	14	14435.41	14	13825.32	17722.3
Ins4	14	14448.69	14	14166.90	17227.3	14	14652.74	14	13994.50	17524.2
Ins5	14	14364.87	14	14050.28	18911.6	14	14497.96	14	14080.56	18118.2
Ins6	10	10964.03	10	10505.65	22632.2	10	11042.72	10	10368.52	21946.1
Ins7	10	11166.59	10	10409.25	23064.5	10	11190.73	10	10712.39	20973.2
Ins8	14	14367.47	14	14096.39	18912.5	14	14435.43	14	14043.17	19009.1
Ins9	10	11155.81	10	10443.68	22991.8	10	11075.43	10	10660.63	23351.0
Ins10	9	11591.68	9	11354.68	88732.5	9	12084.58	9	11381.00	117580.9
Ins11	9	11729.27	9	11113.72	96454.5	9	12119.81	9	11736.44	89607.3
Ins12	9	11773.90	9	11297.07	95143.3	9	12303.97	9	12065.71	84361.5
Ins13	9	11908.33	9	11611.38	88732.3	9	12192.72	9	11764.48	90917.9
Ins14	20	20245.54	20	19721.42	282699.3	20	20734.91	20	20272.06	292065.8
Ins15	20	20247.97	20	19599.61	257154.0	20	20849.27	20	20359.16	254599.7
Ins16	42.97	1597.18	42	1519.54	150523.8	42.6	1644.59	42	1564.39	176528.1
Ins17	42.93	1607.51	42	1531.92	149659.8	42.6	1677.83	42	1604.14	173364.4
Ins18	68	4940.35	68	4691.94	983618.4	68	5112.44	68	4886.56	997854.6
Ins19	68	4903.56	68	4762.24	918579.6	68	5010.80	68	4830.35	908436.1
Avg	21.7	11593.55	21.6	11211.26	173230.34	21.6	11785.79	21.6	11393.65	176826.42
Total	411.9	220277.54	410	213013.85	3291376.37	411.2	223929.95	410	216479.33	3359701.90

Table 6. Experimental results of different methods. LSP and LSC utilize Proximity and Connectivity rules, respectively. # v = the number of vehicles used; ttd = total travel distance; # FE = the number of fitness evaluations.

Instances	LSP					LSC				
	Avg		Best		#FE	Avg		Best		#FE
	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg	# v	ttd	# v	ttd	avg
Ins1	14	15538.88	14	14257.63	23566.7	14	14618.10	14	14312.13	18713.5
Ins2	14.1	15838.67	14	14205.67	22676.8	14	14763.83	14	13969.57	20495.2
Ins3	14	15617.15	14	13959.23	22973.2	14	14847.95	14	13909.70	19703.4
Ins4	14	15780.70	14	14676.79	22972.8	14	14769.49	14	14233.70	22177.2
Ins5	14	14819.55	14	14239.54	22872.9	14	14716.74	14	14292.15	20693.6
Ins6	10	11731.68	10	10689.06	29731.4	10	11332.37	10	10204.95	27894.1
Ins7	10	11468.19	10	10860.74	22703.6	10	11503.04	10	10779.64	26704.1
Ins8	14	15519.73	14	13947.74	26041.9	14	14687.44	14	14125.91	21287.9
Ins9	10	11704.78	10	10593.21	31244.7	10	11333.23	10	10560.55	26919.1
Ins10	9	11613.85	9	11298.03	83050.0	9	12681.51	9	11853.17	100097.1
Ins11	9	11681.91	9	11339.29	83050.3	9	12596.41	9	12115.91	110150.5
Ins12	9	11690.88	9	11307.19	97037.3	9	12453.47	9	11861.15	104468.1
Ins13	9	11865.01	9	11271.52	100096.9	9	12644.87	9	11970.70	97911.6
Ins14	20	20192.06	20	19524.25	284402.6	20	20791.52	20	19620.61	303135.4
Ins15	20	20517.69	20	19658.22	265669.0	20	21154.90	20	20124.10	313353.7
Ins16	43	1594.78	43	1548.55	135429.6	42.6	1719.00	42	1627.14	187577.3
Ins17	43	1579.32	43	1527.47	151760.4	42.9	1672.31	42	1583.43	188646.3
Ins18	68	5019.08	67	4732.18	1150268.0	67.9	5206.57	67	4852.60	1180781.0
Ins19	68	4857.34	68	4682.54	867747.8	68	5106.95	68	4801.95	1099504.7
Avg	21.7	12033.22	21.6	11279.94	181226.1	21.7	12031.56	21.5	11410.48	204748.095
Total	412.1	228631.25	411	214318.87	3443295.9	411.4	228599.69	409	216799.03	3890213.8